

Integrated assessment of simultaneous threshold exceedance of heat, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen across Europe

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Summary

Climate change is expected to elevate exposure to the environmental health risk factors of extreme environmental temperatures, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen. Simultaneous exposure to these can compound the effects. This research brings together modelled data, in conjunction with health-based threshold values to assess whether, where and when there is simultaneous threshold exceedance of heat, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen in Europe for a period in 2022. These results can guide policy makers in pinpointing high-risk areas, particularly vulnerable to simultaneous threshold exceedances, and assist with developing mitigation strategies for those areas.

KEYWORDS: heat stress, air pollution, pollen, co-exposure, WBGT

1. Background

Exposure to multiple environmental health risk factors, including extreme environmental temperatures, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen is expected to increase with climate change. Given their interconnected effects on respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, it is crucial to evaluate these exposures simultaneously, yet comprehensive efforts to do so remain limited. This research aims to develop an approach using modelled data, in conjunction with health-based threshold values, to assess whether, where and when there is simultaneous threshold exceedance of heat, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen in Europe.

2. Methods

To be able to assess simultaneous threshold exceedance of different stressors we retrieved of hourly stressor level data throughout Europe on a 1 by 1 km grid for all three stressors, assigning a value above which a stressor is expected to have an unacceptable negative health effect (i.e., a threshold value) for the individual stressors, and determined hourly for every grid point if threshold exceedance occurred in each grid for the individual stressors and for any combination of stressors.

The modelled time period was from 1 May 2022 until 31 August 2022. We defined exceedance of the threshold if any of the considered stressors in that group were at or above threshold.

The R language was used to process and plot the data in this study. Plots were created using the tmap R package (Tennekes, 2018), hourly ECMWF land (CDS, 2019) and ERA-5 single layer netcdf files for the parameters used in the WBGT calculation were downloaded using emwfr (Hufkens et al., 2020) and imported using ncdf4 (Pierce, 2023). A spatial raster brick (x: longitude, y: latitude, z: time) was created using raster (Hijmans et al., 2023). The R package ‘heatmetrics’ (Spangler et al., 2022) is used for this work with the raster bricks of input meteo data.

2.1. Heat

The basis of the heat stress assessment is the wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT), which is one of the most commonly used indices for indicating heat stress since the 1960s (Blazejczyk et al., 2012). This temperature takes into account the limited evaporative potential in case of high relative humidity, enhanced evaporative potential by ventilation (wind), and additional heat stress when exposed to direct sunlight. The meteorological parameters that are required to calculate the WBGT were obtained from the European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalyses. WBGT ISO 7243 is a screening method for assessment of the heat stress to which a person is exposed (ISO 7243:2017, 2017). We assumed the occurrence of heat stress when the effective WBGT exceeded the recommended alert limit, which takes into account the metabolic activity, clothing types and the acclimatisation status of a person. For this we assumed an unacclimatised person, involved in light activities (i.e., a metabolic rate of 180 W) and no effects of clothing on the WBGT estimate (i.e., a clothing adjusted value of 0).

2.2. Air pollution

Air pollutant hourly concentrations of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃, were simulated with the operational chemical transport model LOTOS-EUROS (Manders et al., 2017). Previous WHO air quality guidelines have been converted by the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) to hourly values based on:

- i) the relation between hourly maxima and corresponding daily averages, and
- ii) daily mortality and daily hospital admissions in relation to air quality (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013).

For PM_{2.5} the ratio between the maximum hourly concentration and 24-hrs average is two, hence we multiplied the WHO threshold value for PM_{2.5} with 2, resulting in an hourly limit concentration value of 30 µg/m³. Using the mortality for all cause data whilst assuming that also daily health complaints will vary according to this ratio, the appropriate limit concentration for both NO₂ and O₃ are estimated at 60 µg/m³. For PM₁₀ a factor of 1.5 is applied, as an approximation to the 66% mass contribution of PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀. Hence the threshold value for PM₁₀ becomes 45 µg/m³.

2.3. Allergenic pollen

Airborne allergenic pollen considered in this work are birch, grass, ragweed, mugwort and alder, for which data was retrieved from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service. There is no commonly agreed upon threshold value for pollen concentrations that will provoke allergy symptoms (Steckling-Muschack et al., 2021) derived a threshold value of 45 grains/m³ based on five studies on birch pollen exposure and drug consumption. A threshold value of 22.6 grains/m³ could be established from four studies examining ragweed pollen and the number of doctor's visits. A review by Prince et al. (Prince et al., 2018) described thresholds for ocular allergy upon grass exposure ranging from 22 – 150 grains/m³.

Levels at which patients developed mild ocular itching or nasal symptoms were at 35 grains/m³. According to the UK Met Office, hay fever symptoms usually appear when the pollen count exceeds 50 grains particles/m³. A reading between 50 and 150 grains/m³ of grass pollen is considered high (Met Office, 2023). Considering all information, a threshold value for airborne allergenic pollen exposure was freely set at 50 grains/m³ in this study, for each of the pollens. Exposure was deemed to occur if any of the pollen levels were above this threshold in each hour, this is considered an occurrence of pollen stress.

The method described above resulted in a European-wide data set with hourly and 1 km² resolution on all stressors and their components. Using the set thresholds, hourly and spatially gridded exceedance (yes/no) of all stressors and combination of stressors were obtained. The total number of hours above

threshold during this period (maximum 2952 hrs) were calculated per 1 by 1 km grid for the three individual stressors and for all of the stressors.

3. Results

The results of the threshold exceedances for each stressor and the overall simultaneous exceedance are described below. **Figure 1** shows the percentage of modelled hours where WBGT exceeded threshold values. **Figure 2** shows the percentage of the modelled period exceeding a threshold for any of the four pollutants considered. **Figure 3** shows the total number of hours exceeding the threshold of 50 grains/m³.

Simultaneous threshold exceedance to heat, one or multiple air pollutants and one or more allergenic pollen occurred less than 5% of the total number of hours for large parts of Northern Europe, that is higher for the south, reaching a maximum of 15.6% of the time in the Cremona region in Northern Italy (**Figure 4**).

Figure 1 Percentage of total hours the WBGT was at or exceeding threshold values.

Figure 2 Percentage of total hours either PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, O₃ were at or exceeding threshold values.

Figure 3 Percentage of total hours pollen was at or exceeding the threshold.

Figure 4 Simultaneous threshold exceedance across Europe of air pollutants and heat and pollen.

4. Conclusion

We present an approach to calculate and visualize simultaneous threshold exceedance of heat, air pollution and airborne allergenic pollen on a 1km² resolution grid for entire Europe. For the studied time period, we found that threshold exceedances to all three stressors simultaneously occurred in varying degrees throughout Europe, but most commonly in Northern Italy.

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Biographies

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